

Concept of Beauty and Ayurveda Medicine

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ABSTRACT

Beauty of a person provides happiness or satisfaction. Beauty provides pride and confidence to some range and happiness also. *Ayurveda* has never isolated the connection of mental and spiritual health from the concept of beauty. *Ayurveda* decides the beauty by *Sara* (Structural dominance), *Prakriti* (Body constitution) *Sanhanana* (Body density), *Pramana* (Measurement), *Twaka* (Skin complexion), and *Dirghayu Lakshana* (Signs of long life). Beauty care in *Ayurveda* starts from the mothers' womb and also from *Dinacharya* (Day routine), *Ratricharya* (Night routine), *Ritucharya* (Seasonal routine) with the practice of medicinal herbs and minerals. According to *Ayurveda* noxious substance which present in our body reason behind the ugliness and diseased of a person. *Shodhana* (Purification) is the prime therapeutic procedure to eliminate body toxins. In *Charaka Samhita Acharya Charaka* mentioned cosmetic drugs as, *Kushtaghna*, *Varnya*, *Kandughna* etc. and many *Pralepa* (Poultice) are narrated in *Sushruta Samhita* by *Acharya Sushruta* and *Ashtanga Hridaya* by *Acharya Vagbhata*. For beautification of hairs, skin, teeth, nails etc. some medicinal plants have been prescribed like- *Haridra*, *Sariva*, *Manjishtha*, *Amalaki*, *Chandana*, *Babool*, *Grikumari*, *Sikakai*, *Lavanga*, *Brinaraj*, *Ritha* etc. *Ahar* (Diet) has a special part in maintaining and improving beauty of an individual person. *Panchakarma* procedures are useful for beautification of skin. In skin diseases like Vitiligo, Psoriasis, Eczema and Acne Vulgaris *Ayurveda* has already proved itself. In global cosmetic industry India could come out as a major contributor. This can be possible, as one of the strengths of Indian tradition is *Ayurveda*.

KEYWORDS: Beauty care, Shodhana, Varnya, Amalaki, Vitiligo

INTRODUCTION

Every individual wants himself or herself beautiful. Beauty makes our senses feel happy. Beauty is not mention only for females but men also. There are few individual who are born beautiful and some wish to become beautiful. In *Ayurveda* the concept of using *Aushadha Dravaya* or herbs for beautification is well explained. In India the cosmetic formulations are used for praising and for pleasure since *Vedic* period. The external local application of *Tilaka* (tika), *Anjana* (kajala), *Aguru*, *Haridra*, *Chandana* etc. to God and Goddess are seen in many ceremony of India^[1,2] According to the Drugs and Cosmetics Act (India) 1940 cosmetics may be defined as any substance intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled, or otherwise applied to human body for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness. Cosmetology is the science of alternation of appearance and modification of beauty. Any material or formulations considered to be placed in contact with the many external areas of human body mainly for clearing, correcting body odors or protecting them and changing their appearance and keeping them in good conditions are included in this.^[3] *Ayurveda* focus on external and internal beauty. It is said that a self fulfillment person is forever beautiful and not use any external cosmetics or designer clothes. There are some

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secret way of physical beauty in *Ayurveda* like *Ayurvedic* therapies, treatment and advice. According to *Ayurveda Ama* (toxins) free body, improve cellular nutrition, smooth removal and the balance of the *Dosha* resulting health development, beauty management and healing. *Ahar* (Diet) and lifestyle are two major things which help to gain good health and beauty. As per *Ayurveda* beauty is close part of the human personality so it associates to each and every aspect of the mind, body and the soul. To accomplish of natural beauty, deep cleansing and re-balancing procedures are helpful, which can be accomplished by using *Ayurveda's* standard rejuvenation procedure. The rejuvenation procedure teaches ways to become naturally beautiful, not just limited to the physical body but extends to subtle qualities and vitality of a person. So, rejuvenation therapy is considered as an essential part of ongoing self-care that helps beauty be with you to whole life and a new start in the process of making health-supporting lifestyle changes. Consumer trends suggest a gradual shift from chemical-based products to *Ayurvedic* beauty products. Increasing concern over side effects of chemical-based products is the special reason behind this trend.^[4]

Concept of Beauty in Ayurveda

Ayurveda decides the beauty by *Sara* (Structural dominance), *Prakriti* (Body constitution) *Sanhanana* (Body density), *Pramana* (Measurement), *Twaka* (Skin complexion), and *Dirghayu Lakshana* (Signs of long life). Beauty care in Ayurveda starts from the mothers' womb and also from *Dinacharya* (Day routine), *Ratricharya* (Night routine), *Ritucharya* (Seasonal routine) with the practice of medicinal herbs and minerals. According to Ayurveda noxious substance which present in our body reason behind the ugliness and diseased of a person. *Shodhana* (Purification) is the prime therapeutic procedure to eliminate body toxins. Beauty provides pride and confidence to some range and happiness also. According to *Acharya Charaka* finding a suitable man increased the beauty of a female and vice versa. Beautiful lady is always appreciated in our ancient text as goodness, prosperity and creation. There was a distribution for nominating a beautiful woman (*Kalinee*) in the *Rasasala* (pharmacy) for *Rasabandha* and the quality of *Kalinee* is well mentioned in *Rasaratna Samuchachaya* and *Anandakanda*. If the *Kalinee* is not available then the specific way to convert ordinary woman to *Kalinee* is also possible by the administration of one *Karsha* (12 gm) of purified sulphur along with ghee for twenty one days.^[5]

In Ayurveda human body functions by various channel systems is called as "*Srotansi*", containing both microscopic and macroscopic structures such as the respiratory system, lymphatic/ circulatory system, reproductive system and nervous systems, among others. These channels work as numerous psychobiological processes such as enzyme production, neuro transmitter secretion, hormonal intelligence, respiratory capacity and digestive assimilation/ elimination, immune power etc. and responsible for fitness and beauty. These act smoothly and in concern with one another to execute complex decision making concerning the supply of nutrients, filtration of toxins, excretion of wastes and much more. If these waste materials are insufficiently metabolized, toxins or incompletely processed foods can get deposited in weaker tissues of the body. If unaddressed, these can become a disease. Weak zones occur in the body due to genetic factors or more commonly, lifestyle factors, such as unhealthy food choices, stress or environmental influences. These toxins or unprocessed metabolic deposits can cloud the normal psycho-biological cellular intelligence and vanish body luster and beauty.

Panchakarma therapy is both inhibitory for healthy people to maintain and improve superb cellular function, and therapeutic for those experiencing disease. According to Ayurveda *Ama* (noxious substance) which present in our body reason behind the ugliness and diseased of a person. *Shodhana/ Panchakarma* (Purification) is the prime therapeutic procedure to eliminate body toxins. It is a very complex and experienced science of purification of the body and mind. Water is a major component for keeping skin in healthy condition. Water present in the deeper epidermal layers moves upward to hydrate cells in the stratum corneum in the skin, at last being lost to evaporation. *Snehana* and *Swedana* moisturize the skin, provide more elasticity and rejuvenate skin tissues. As cells of our face make their way to the surface over their lifecycle, they die and become saturated with keratin, or skin debris. Keratin is important because it protects the skin from the external elements but the shedding of that outer layer can unclog pores.

Ayurveda medicine as Cosmetics

In *Charaka Samhita Acharya Charaka* mentioned cosmetic drugs as, *Kushtaghna*, *Varnya*, *Kandughna* etc. and many *Pralepa* (Poultice) are narrated in *Sushruta Samhita* by *Acharya Sushruta* and *Ashtanga Hridaya* by *Acharya Vagbhatta*. The very common and well accepted ones are *Chandanadi Lepa*, *Kumkumadi Lepa*, *Dasana Samskar Churna*, *Dashanga Lepa*, *Kukumadi Taila*, *Himasagar Taila*, *Nilibringaraj Taila*, etc. Buttermilk and goat's milk traditionally used in Indian face mask formulations have soothing and moisturizing properties. They also contain vitamin A, B6, B12 and E. They can make helpful alternatives to chemical bases and emollients. *Shikakai* is a traditional herb used in hair shampoos. The material is extracted from the *Shikakai* pods, collected from *Acacia concinna* shrub. The pods are rich in saponins and make a mild detergent, which has a neutral pH. *Ritha* powder, extracted from Soap nuts (*Sapindus pericarp*) also contains saponins, which acts as a foaming agent. It was used as soap in Ayurvedic tradition. The oils also maintain integrity of cosmetic products and can be used as a base instead of petroleum and plastic derivatives. There are significant evidences already generated for Ayurveda skin care in vitiligo, psoriasis and eczema and acne vulgaris.^[6]

The Ayurvedic cosmetics may be grouped under ^[6,7] -

1. Cosmetics for enhancing appearance of facial skin.
2. Cosmetics for hair growth and care.
3. Cosmetics for skin care, especially in teenager (acne, pimples and sustaining).
4. Shampoos, soaps, powders and perfumery, etc.
5. Miscellaneous products

➤ List of medicinal plants listed in Ayurveda, proven to be having cosmoceutical properties:

A. Medicinal plants used as moisturizers, skin tonics & anti aging-

1. *Aloe vera* – Moisturizer, Sunscreen & Emollient.
2. *Calendula officinalis* – Wound healing.
3. *Cichorium intybus* – Skin blemishes
4. *Curcuma longa* - Antiseptic, Antibacterial, Improves complexion
5. *Daucus carota* – Natural toner and skin rejuvenator
6. *Glycyrrhiza glabra* – Skin whitening
7. *Ocimum sanctum* - Anti-aging, Antibacterial & Antiseptic
8. *Rosa damascena* - Toning & Cooling
9. *Rosmarinus officinalis* -Skin rejuvenator & Cleansing
10. *Rubia cordifolia* – Wound healing & Anti-aging
11. *Triticum sativum* – Antioxidant, Skin nourishes, anti-wrinkle

B. Sun Screen

1. *Aloe vera* – Moisturizer
2. *Suticum sativum* - Antioxidant

C. Sun Tan

1. *Cyperus rotundus*
2. *Moringa oliefera*

Discussion

The market for Ayurvedic beauty products is increasing fast. Many companies are involved with branded products in categories such as skin care, hair care, soaps and essential oils. Due to harmful chemicals in beauty products has increased customer interest in natural cosmetics. More and more products now mention in herbal and botanical

ingredients. Consumption for these products is increasing at 8%.^[8] Today, India is entering the cosmetics industry in a big way.

Conclusion

Ayurveda is an ancient medicinal science in which using herbs and other natural ingredients.^[9] *Ayurveda* products and Indian herbs are being sourced and tested for use in the cosmetics industry and practiced in beauty parlors.^[10] These herbs are currently used in their raw form, dried into powders or pulverized with pestle and mortar. The end product contains a large amount of inactive unnecessary compounds. The products are often biologically ineffective because there aren't enough active components in the formulae. The concentration and action of bioactive compounds extracted from herbs have to be increased.^[11,12] These formulae have to be tested in scientific trials with an evidence based approach. These could emerge as a major contributor to the global cosmetic industry.

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